

THE LEADERSHIP OF MADRASAH PRINCIPALS IN IMPROVING LEARNING QUALITY AT MADRASAH TSANAWIYAH NEGERI KOTO DIAN KECAMATAN KELILING DANAU KABUPATEN KERINCI

E Putra¹,Rimin¹, Yuserizal Bustami¹

¹State Islamic Institute of Kerinci, Kerinci-Jambi

yuserizal888@gmail.com

Abstract

This study took place in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci Regency. Selection of this setting was based on the consideration of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency where it is one of the Madrasahs that has many limitations affected the management of the school as a whole. So the researcher rose the main issue of the study. To know how the pattern of leadership on the head of madrasah in improving the quality of learning in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency. To know factors influencing leadership of madrasah head in improving quality of learning at Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci Regency. To find out what efforts made by Madrasah Principals in improving the quality of learning in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci.

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.2540618

1. Introduction

The research method used to study the leadership of madrasah principals in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci Regency was a qualitative method. Based on the problems faced, this was studied by using an educational perspective, with a descriptive analytical approach supported by data obtained from literatures and documents related to the problems studied. Data collection was carried out by researcher to get information of desired data, in this case researcher used instruments; interview, observation, and documentation. Data analysis used in this research was data flow analysis model. According to Miles and Huberman (year), principle data analysis activity is during the research activity (during data collection), and the most core activities include data deduction (data reduction), data presentation (display data) as well as drawing conclusions (making conclusion), observation/ persistence, triangulation techniques, and consultation mentors. The implications of this study were: 1) the principal needs support by all parties, both consistent principals to realize the achieving school and the quality of the students themselves as well as adequate facilities and infrastructure, 2) the existence of learning facilities for teachers can not be eliminated, the learning facilities is useful to help teachers conduct learning activities effectively and efficiently, 3) three factors that must exist and greatly determine the educational and learning activities; teachers, students, and learning instruments. The absence of any of these factors can affect the educational and learning process.

2. Discussion

The head of the madrasah is the person responsible for the achievement of the school's objectives, especially in relation to the quality of education as well as the customer satisfaction of the teachers

internally and the parents of the students externally. In order to obtain quality and customer satisfaction, the principal should have a friendly attitude and open to subordinates. The principal also means a profession that demands the mastery of a number of abilities and competencies. Thus, the person appointed to be the principal must firstly obtain educational **prajabatan** earlier. According to Mulyono (year) cited by Wahab and Umiarso (year), the principal of madrasah should have some requirements to create madrasah that they lead to be an effective madrasah such as have good physical and spiritual health, sticking to the goals achieved, excited, proficient in giving guidance, honest, smart and competent in terms of teaching and paying good attention and striving to achieve it. Apart from these requirements, the Regulation of the Minister of National Education of Indonesian Republic number 13 of 2007 on principal standards of Madrasah also states about the competencies that must be owned by the Principal of Madrasah; personality, managerial, entrepreneurship, supervision, and social. The quality of madrasah in general can be seen from several aspects; 1) formulation of vision, mission and goals, 2) teacher competence and other human resources, 3) development of the curriculum, 4) effectiveness of teaching and learning process, 5) relevance of facilities and infrastructure, 6) accuracy of evaluation, and 7) quality of input and output of learners. Quality assurance of formal, nonformal and informal education as written in the regulation of the Minister of National Education number 63 in 2009 on the quality assurance system of education, is a systematic and integrated activities in the implementation of education to improve the nation's intelligence life. Systematic and integrated activities are carried out by educational units, the implementation of educational units, local government, government, and the community as well as involving the business world. Based on the observations that the researchers did, the principal should be able to guide, organize, influence, mobilize, and coordinate the implementation of educational tasks in improving the quality of learning. The indication showed that leadership pattern in Madrasah was not yet fully run, there were still teachers who had not been able to properly analyze the subject matter, and learners can not compete with other schools. Based on the previous discussion, then in this section, the researchers pointed out several points as a result of the main problem analysis, research objectives, theory exposure and research results. The conclusions can be described as follows.

1. Leadership Pattern on Head of Madrasah in MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency

In implementing the rules and regulations in Madrasah, the head of the madrasah as the top leader applies a democratic and participative leadership model. Where in implementing the order, the head of the madrasah always refers to the rules that have been mutually agreed upon. In implementing the leadership functions, the head of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency is more dominant in implementing the function of equating the shared vision of empowering the members through cooperative working team, giving examples and awakening the soul to continuously improve technical skills and interpersonal skills. Thus, supervision is the success of the management process. Therefore, supervision needs to be viewed comprehensively, because this oversight function is the answer between planning and procurement and also the implementation, maintenance, and mining of the management process. The results of interviews with the head of madrasah and staff of MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci regency on the leadership patterns of madrasah heads in improving the quality of learning, it is correct but not quite right, because according to the theory expressed by Mulyasa that the head of a successful school should be able to develop management and leadership and understand the full vision of his school.

2. Factors Influencing the Head Leadership of Madrasah in Improving the Quality of Learning at MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency

Factors that constrain the head of the madrasah in improving teacher discipline lead to two main issues; social sensitivity and the influence of local culture, in addition with the factor of educational financing.

a. Internal and External Factors

In the process of education and teaching in a school can be influenced by internal factors and external Factors for both the head of Madrasah, teachers and students at MtsN Koto Dian Kerinci regency. Those factors can be inadequate facilities and infrastructure, concerning the quality of teachers, curriculum, teaching and learning process, and other supporting facilities such as administrative staff and libraries which are all one system in the context of the transfer process of teaching, so those factors are not located on the results. If these factors are met well and have quality then in turn will produce and improve the quality of education in schools. This illustrates that a head of madrasah should be responsible for all madrasah development plans, have clear objectives, manage finances, oversee learning programs, and prepare planning reports. Thus, the head of the madrasah as a manager in the organization of the madrasah should be the pattern of leadership improved in such a way as to improve the quality of learning in the madrasah.

3. Efforts Made by the Head of Madrasah in Improving the Quality of Learning in MTSN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency

The efforts made by the head of the madrasah in improving the discipline of teachers are be *tauladan* for all elements of madrasah in terms of obeying the rules and regulations of madrasah, imposing daily attendance, and having interpersonal approach to teachers. Based on the observation and interviews data with principals and some teachers, it can be understood that the efforts of the principal in managing facilities and infrastructure to improve the quality of learning in MtsN Koto Dian Kerinci Regency is good and right, although there are factors that affect in the realization while the leadership of the principal of MtsN Koto Dian of Kerinci Regency in managing the school should be appreciated only how the principal is fully responsible for the maintenance of facilities and infrastructure in the school, with always maintained so as not to be easily damaged and still able to be used with the best.

Additionally, based on the observation and interviews with the head of madrasah and some teachers, it can be concluded that the efforts of the head madrasah in improving the quality of learning in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci, there has been an effort from the principal to overcome and improve leadership in improving the quality of learning in madrasah. That is the head of Madrasahs creates the quality of the learning experience. This aims to improve the quality of education in order to become more qualified. Improving the quality of learning with an interpersonal approach model is a psychological effort in providing understanding to teachers and administrative personnel in terms of how to create a good madrasah environment.

Implications

The implications expressed in this section refer to the conclusions mention earlier are the leadership of the madrasah head is still weak and needs revamping in the future to revise more realistic teacher discipline improvement program. To achieve achievement educational institutions, the educational institutions need to have good administrative management education. These activities involve all the arrangement activities or arrangements to establish a group of people to achieve goals such as teachers and employees. In relation to that, the teaching administration being the head of the madrasah's assessment includes the annual program learning plan, the semester program, the teaching preparation, the improvement program and the enrichment. Some of these aspects become the main priority concept of madrasah head in assessing teacher discipline. Furthermore, the head of the madrasah has not been able to work on

planning, organizing activities, directing, coordinating and conducting supervision, evaluating activities, determining policies, holding meetings, making decisions and organizing learning processes to achieve organizational goals, while he has not been able to empower all resources communities and the environment that aims to educate the life of the nation, including its responsibility in the distribution of teachers in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency. Leadership of madrasah head in improving the quality of learning needs to arrange in general all aspects of madrasah that have a link with the teacher, so that teachers can work professionally and competence maximally as supervision of teacher discipline. Absolute supervision should be carried out by the head of the madrasah considering the function of the head as a supervisor, the head of the madrasah must supervise the class at least twice in one semester. In fact, the head of a madrasah only adopts a policy of delegating supervisory duties to the deputy head of the madrasah in the curriculum field, or a senior teacher who has the competence in supervision. If the head of the madrasah has no opportunity to carry it out by himself, the supervision of the class carried out by the head of madrasah can not run properly, it shows the weakness of leadership, especially in the field of supervision both conducted by the local department of education and internal supervision conducted by the head of madrasah.

The leadership of madrasah head in upbringing has close links and needs to be synchronized in aligning the attainment of the more realistic educational objectives of Madrasah Tsanawiyah Madrasah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci. In planning the teacher discipline evaluation program, the head of the madrasah also establishes short-term goals, medium-term assessments, and long-term assessments. In the short-term preferred assessment, the most important is the factor of teacher presence, *istiqamah*, and discipline. Medium-term assessments focus on teacher quality and classroom supervision, and on long-term assessments focus on the totality of teacher quality improvement, professional evaluation, and teacher mapping. Based on data from several opinions and search results in the field of research, the researchers conclude that the coaching of extracurricular activities becomes a necessity in improving discipline in the madrasah environment, especially in personal discipline of each teacher in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency. Because with the formation of teachers, it will motivate students to always follow in complying with all rules established together. This condition is one of important points for madrasah head in disciplinary development at the madrasah, with the policy of the headmaster in giving responsibility to the teacher to guide the students in carrying out extracurricular activities into concrete steps in shaping and cultivating discipline, especially among teachers. In viewing the success or failure of disciplinary coaching, it can be seen from the end of the guidance conducted by the teacher, whether the students built the progress as expected, or even declined. Overall, teachers are one of the determinants of success or failure of an education because education will be responsible for the personal formation of students. Thus, the administrative management of teachers in Madrasah Tsanawiyah Negeri Koto Dian Kerinci regency aimed towards increasing the quality of madrasah. The head of a professional democratic madrasah through professional appointments also helps this process. This will foster a democratic climate in madrasah, which will encourage a conducive climate for the creation of optimal learning quality to develop the potential of learners. The head of a madrasah is a person who is really expected to be a leader. Therefore, the leadership quality of madrasah head determines good and bad management of personnel administration (teacher). Teacher management requires highly independent and professional madrasah heads with strong administrative skills, in order to be able to take decisions and initiatives to improve the quality of madrasah.

References

- [1] Danim S 2008 *Visi Baru Manajemen Sekolah dari Unit Birokrasi ke Lembaga Akademik* (Jakarta: Bumi Aksara)
- [2] Fattah N 2012 *Sistem Penjaminan Mutu Pendidikan* (Jakarta: PT. Remaja Rosdakarya)
- [3] Maisah 2013 *Manajemen Pendidikan* (Jakarta: Gaung Persada Press Group)
- [4] Makbuloh D 2001 *Manajemen Mutu Pendidikan Islam* (Jakarta:PT. Raja Grafindo Persada)
- [5] Peraturan Menteri Pendidikan Nasional Republik Indonesia nomor 13 Tahun 2007 tentang Standar Kepala Sekolah/ Madrasah.
- [6] Wahab A dan Umiarso 2011 *Kepemimpinan Pendidikan dan Kecerdasan Spiritual* (Jakarta: Ar Ruzz Media)

